

PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF ADOLESCENTS IN RELATION TO GENDER, LOCALE AND TYPE OF SCHOOL

Dr. Suman Kumari

Assistant Professor, Education, Abhilashi University Chail Chowk, Mandi, H. P.

Dr. Reena

Assistant Professor , Education, Abhilashi University Chail Chowk, Mandi, H. P.

ABSTRACT

The main aim of the present investigation was to study psychological well-being of adolescents in relation to gender, locale and type of school. For conducting this study, a sample of 200 adolescents (100 boys and 100 girls) from different government and private schools was selected from Solan district of Himachal Pradesh by adopting stratified random sampling technique. Data were collected with help of Psychological Well-Being Scale by Dr. Devendra Singh Sisodia & Ms. Pooja Choudary (2012). Means, S.D. and t-test were used for analysis of data. The findings of the study revealed that girls were significantly more psychologically well as compared to boys. Furthermore, it was concluded that the rural adolescents had better psychological well-being than urban adolescents. It was also concluded that government school adolescents had better psychological well-being as compared to private school adolescents. In the end of the paper, implications have been discussed.

KEYWORD: Psychological Well-Being.

INTRODUCTION

Well-being is an ongoing process, not an intermittent prescription: it is based on individual's active interaction in a complex world. The concept of well-being is dimension of attitudes, behaviour, thoughts and feeling which can enhance a sense of well-being and influence the individual's attention of self-care and compliance with medical regimens. Psychological well-being is broader concept that includes experiencing pleasant emotions, the level of negative mood and high life satisfaction. It is not only the lack disease or illness or absence of anxiety or depression. It is state of complete physical and social health. Psychological well-being articulates different challenge individuals encounter as they strive to function individuals experience warm and trusting relationships, feel that they are developing as individuals, have purpose in their lives, feel that they can shape the world around them to fit their needs and feel capable to direct their actions from internet standards. Srimathi and Kumar (2010) revealed that women employees working in industries had least psychological well-being in all the sub-factors and total psychological well-being scores, followed by women working in health organizations. Women employees working in banks had medium level of psychological well-being scores. Women teachers had highest total psychological well-being scores and also in the entire sub factors of psychological well-being. Omar, Alam and Zahoor (2011) revealed that male police personal were well placed in terms of both emotional intelligence and psychological well-being. Furthermore, high positive correlation was found between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being. Panahi, Yunus and Roslan (2013) showed that marital and employment status had a significant difference in autonomy while, the marital status showed positive and significant difference for overall

psychological well-being, positive relationship, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. However, there were no significant differences in psychological well-being of graduate students across different races and family sizes. Sharma and Tankha (2014) revealed that male students of science faculty were significantly higher on four factors of psychological well-being namely environmental mastery, positive relations with others, purpose in life and self-acceptance than the commerce students. Akhter (2015) Showed that significant gender differences in the levels on psychological well-being. It means male and female students were difference in psychological well-being. Brouzos et al. (2016) revealed that significant correlations between meaning in life and subjective or psychological well-being among adolescents. It is highlighted that the significance of particular sources of meaning in life, such as fair treatment and achievement, in promoting students' well-being. Easow and Ghorpade (2017) indicated that majority of the adolescents had adequate psychological well-being but those in moderate level associated with some factors such as control of self and events, self-esteem, mental balance, social environment and sociability. There was significant association between the psychological well-being of high school adolescents with gender and family origin of the adolescents. Udhayakumar and Illango (2018) revealed that the majority of the students were classified as experiencing 'high level' regarding positive wellbeing and 'high' regarding anxiety and depressed mood. Gomez Lopez et al. (2019) showed that a romantic relationship was an important source of well-being for both adolescents and emerging adults. Dhanabhakym and Sarath (2023) concluded that psychological well-being is an important aspect of mental and emotional health that requires on-going attention and care. Individuals can promote their psychological well-being by engaging in activities that promote personal growth, maintain positive relationships, and provide a sense of purpose and meaning in life. Additionally, individuals can seek support from mental health professionals if they experience difficulties with their psychological well-being. By taking a holistic approach to promoting mental and emotional health, individuals can enhance their overall well-being and lead a fulfilling life.

On the basis of review of related literature, it may be summed up that psychological well-being of adolescents is highly essential in present times of cut-throat competition. Hence, present study was undertaken with following objectives:

OBJECTIVES

1. To study gender-wise difference in psychological well-being of adolescents.
2. To study locale-wise difference in psychological well-being of adolescents.
3. To study the difference in psychological well-being of adolescents studying in government and private schools.

HYPOTHESES

1. There will be no significant gender-wise difference in psychological well-being of adolescents.
2. There will be no significant locale-wise difference in psychological well-being of adolescents.
3. There will be no significant difference in psychological well-being of adolescents studying in government and private schools.

METHODOLOGY

For conducting the present investigation, survey technique under descriptive method of research was employed.

SAMPLING

The sample of the study consisted of 200 adolescents (100 boys and 100 girls). Stratified random sampling technique was employed to select the sample from different government and private schools of Solan district of Himachal Pradesh.

RESEARCH TOOL USED

The data were collected by using Psychological Well Being Scale by Dr. Devendra Singh Sisodia & Ms. Pooja Choudary (2012).

ANALYSIS OF DATA

The data were analyzed with the help of descriptive statistics and t-test was used to study differences in psychological well-being of adolescents in relation to gender, locale and type of school.

MAIN FINDINGS

The mean psychological well-being scores of adolescents with respect to gender, locale and type of school along with number, SDs and t-values are given Table 1.

TABLE 1

MEANS, STANDARD DEVIATIONS, STANDARD ERROR OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN MEANS AND T-VALUES IN RESPECT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF ADOLESCENTS WITH RESPECT TO THEIR GENDER, LOCALE AND TYPE OF SCHOOL

Variables		Mean	S.D.	SE _{dm}	d _f	t-value
Gender	Boys	184.20	20.95	2.10	198	2.06*
	Girls	190.03	18.95	1.89		
Locale	Rural	187.60	22.14	2.21	198	0.34 (NS)
	Urban	186.63	18.02	1.80		
Type of School	Government	187.78	19.84	1.98	198	0.47 (NS)
	Private	186.45	20.51	2.05		

* Significant at 0 .05 level of significance. NS- --Not Significant.

From Table 1, it is clear that the mean psychological well-being score of female adolescents is 190.03 which is higher than male adolescents (184.20). The calculated t-value for mean difference in psychological well-being scores of boys and girls was found to be 2.06 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance, for d_f 198. This implies that there exists significant difference in psychological well-being of male and female adolescents. Hence, it may be interpreted that the girls were significantly more psychologically well as compared to boys.

On the other hand, the mean psychological well-being score of rural adolescents is 187.60 which is little higher than urban adolescents (186.63). The calculated t-value for mean difference in psychological well-being scores of rural and urban adolescents was found to be 0.34 which is not significant even at 0.05 level of significance, for d_f 198. This implies that

there exists no significant difference in psychological well-being among rural and urban adolescents. Hence, it may be interpreted that rural and urban adolescents were almost equally psychologically well.

Further, the mean score of psychological well-being in respect of government school adolescents is 187.78 which is somewhat higher than the mean psychological well-being score of private school adolescents (186.45). The calculated t-value for mean difference in psychological well-being of adolescents with respect to their type of school was found to be 0.47 which is not significant even at 0.05 level of significance, for d_f 198. This implies that there exists no significant difference in psychological well-being of adolescents studying in government schools or in private schools.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS AND IMPLICATIONS

The present investigation was conducted to study psychological well-being of adolescents in relation to gender, locale and type of school. Girls reflected significantly more psychological well-being score as compared to boys. However, no significant differences were observed in psychological well-being of adolescents with respect to locale and type of school. On the basis of these findings, it may be suggested that life skill education as well as value education must be given an important place in the school curriculum. Traditional methods of education require change to cope-up with the changes in whole educational scenario. Changes in the present evaluation system will certainly reduce the phobia of Board Examination among the adolescents which will contribute towards psychological well-being among them. The schools should organize programmes from time to time to guide parents to provide healthy and wholesome environment to children to develop them into balanced personality with a healthy approach towards life.

Orientation programme may be held in schools from time to time where experts from different walks of life can be introduced to the adolescents. Special lectures and discussions targeted towards the major problems leading to poor mental health of adolescents can be organized. Counseling is now-a-days getting much significance in the schools. A counseling corner must be set-up in each and every school where students can discuss their problems freely and have important directions and information from the counselor.

The meetings of Parents Teachers Association (PTA) or School Management Committees (SMCs) should be held from time to time not only for discussing the overall functional policies of the school, but serious deliberations should also be conducted on problems faced by adolescents such as depression, anxiety and frustration. Techniques like cooperative learning, group discussions, brain storming sessions and team teaching can also be successful in having a deep insight into adolescents' behaviour and providing them directions to resolve their problems themselves and find out the best kind of reaction to it.

REFERENCES

1. Gomez-Lopez; Mercedes, Viejo, Carmen and Ortega-Ruiz, Rosario (2019). Well-being and romantic relationships: A systematic review in adolescence and emerging adulthood. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16, 1-31.
2. Udhayakumar, P. and Illango, P. (2018). Psychological wellbeing among college students. *Journal of Social Work Education and Practice*, 3(2), 79-89. Retrieved from www.jswep.in on dated 14-07-2019.

3. Panahi; Soheila, Md Yunus, Aida Suraya Bt. and Roslan, Samsilah Bt. (2013). Correlates of psychological well-being amongst graduate students in Malaysia. Report Opinion, 5(8), 39-49. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencepub.net/report> on dated 14-07-2019.
4. Srimathi, N. L., and Kumar, Kiran, S. K. (2010). Psychological well-being of employed women across different organizations. Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology, 36(1), 89-95.
5. Easow, Robin Jacob and Ghorpade, Pavana (2017). Level of psychological well-being among adolescents in a selected high school at Tumkur. IOSR Journal of Nursing and Health Science, 6(4), 74-78. Retrieved from www.iosrjournals.org on dated 12-07-2019.
6. Brouzos; Andreas, Vassilopoulos, Stephanos P. and Boumpouli, Christina (2016). Adolescents' subjective and psychological well-being: the role of meaning in life. Hellenic Journal of Psychology, 13, 153-169.
7. Sharma, Jyotika and Geetika, Tankha (2014). Psychological well-being of first year male students of science and commerce faculty. Research Journal of Social Science & Management, 4(7), 62-70.
8. Omar, Alam and Zahoor (2011). Relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being of male police personal. Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology, 37(1), 47-52.
9. Akhter, Sana (2015). Psychological well-being in student of gender difference. The International Journal of Indian Psychology, 2(4), 53-161. Retrieved from <http://www.ijip.in> on dated 13-07-2019.
10. Dhanabhakyaam, M. and Sarath M. (2023). Psychological Wellbeing: Asystematic Literature Review. International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology (IJARSCT), 3(1), 603-607.